

Interview

“The socio-emotional divide in Human-AI Collaboration”

General Questions

- Tell me about yourself:
 - Role
 - Experience in Software Engineering field (in years)
 - Experience in using AI support for SE tasks (in years)
 - Domain of the current organisation

General Questions

- What AI tools or systems do you use in your software engineering tasks? (Types of Tasks)
- How do you perceive their effectiveness in helping your SE tasks you explained above?
- Have you used AI for any decision-making tasks?
 - How effective was it to use it for decision-making?

Socio- emotional Intelligence (SEI)

- **Emotional intelligence** is the ability to recognize and appropriately react to our own and others' emotional state.
 - (Emotional intelligence (emotional quotient (EQ)) is the ability to perceive, assess, generate, understand, and control emotions.)
- **Social intelligence** is learning from and adapting to social situations, with skills such as “reading the room” and exercising tact.
 - (Social intelligence (social quotient (SQ)) is the capacity to understand other humans and to act both rationally and emotionally in relation to others. SQ is important, particularly when forming social bonds and when working within a team.)

Key socio-emotional aspects that can influence collaboration

- Which socio-emotional attributes do you expect in a human teammate when you do collaboration for SE tasks?
- Do you think an AI teammate to have any of the above said traits? If so which ones and why?

Given this list of Socio-emotional traits:

- Which socio-emotional attributes do you expect in a human partner when you do collaboration for SE tasks?
- Do you think an AI teammate to have any of the above said traits? If so which ones and why?

SEI Traits	Description
Emotional Self-Awareness	Recognizing one's emotions and their effects
Emotional Self-Control	Keeping disruptive emotions and impulses in check
Adaptability	Flexibility in handling change
Achievement Orientation	Striving to improve or meet excellence
Positive Outlook	Seeing the positive aspects of things and the future
Empathy	Sensing others' feelings and concerns
Organizational Awareness	Understanding group emotions and power dynamics
Influence	Using effective persuasion tactics
Coach and Mentor	Supporting others' growth and abilities
Conflict Management	Negotiating and resolving disagreements
Inspirational Leadership	Inspiring and guiding individuals and groups
Teamwork	Collaborating toward shared goals
Systems Thinking	Understanding multiple causal relationships
Pattern Recognition	Identifying patterns in complex information

Ranking

- **Now can you rank the SEI traits in the table given here based on your expectation from AI as a collaborating teammate?**
- Do you believe an AI partner to have social and emotional intelligence to have better collaboration? Why (example) or why not?
- Can you think of any instance from your experience with AI tools, when lack of socio-emotional intelligence in AI affected your collaboration with it?

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Challenges due to the socio-emotional divide in HAIC in SE

1. What specific challenges do you face when collaborating with AI, due to its lack of socio-emotional traits?(socio-emotional divide)
2. How do these challenges differ from those you experience with human team members?
3. What changes or improvements would you suggest for making AI systems more collaborative through socio-emotional awareness?
4. How do you expect the future of human-AI collaboration in software engineering?

Anything else you would like to add??